

IMPROVING LISTENING SKILLS USING ANIMATION APPROACH

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Abstract. *In this article will be discussed about the demand and importance of learning foreign languages, how to speak foreign languages, development of listening skills through the use of modern and effective methods of technology.*

Keywords: *Speaking and listening skills, modern methods, watching cartoons, and video materials.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье речь пойдет о необходимости и важности изучения иностранных языков, о том, как говорить на иностранных языках, о развитии навыков аудирования посредством использования современных и эффективных методов техники.*

Ключевые слова: *навыки говорения и аудирования, современные методики, просмотр мультфильмов и видеоматериалов.*

The success of listening comprehension depends on several factors, the most important of which are individual age characteristics of the listener, speed of perception, and conditions (speed, amount and size of information, supports of perception). Listening comprehension is closely related to reading and speaking types of speech activity. Because of this, the types of speech activity have similarities and differences. These are the following: Reading, listening, and reading are receptive types of speech activity because they are aimed at receiving information. This type of speech activity is precognition and assumption.[1]

Today, learning foreign languages has become the need of the tense. The demand for learning foreign languages has been increasing day by day since the independence of our country. Due to the high development of the internet in Uzbekistan, language learners can use all the facilities they need. Now, there are modern computers in all schools, colleges, and universities and any user can access the internet through them. Another main purpose of using contemporary technologies is that they help to learn foreign languages without difficulty. The most common method of modern approaches is the use of multimedia in the lessons.[2] The advantage of multimedia tools is that when learning a foreign language with their help, you can learn by watching live games, and pictures, listening to sounds, and watching the activities of live games. Also, among the four skills that are important in learning any foreign language, listening is at the top. Usually in the process of learning and teaching a language, the main emphasis is placed on writing and speaking in that language, and these skills are seen as the main factors of language use. We can see that listening and reading skills are second. One of the reasons for this may be that it is somewhat difficult to master listening skills but as mentioned above, as technology has developed, learning listening comprehension through different materials has made this situation much easier. In addition, students and pupils are realizing that it is important to improve listening skills in the course of the lesson, and it is recommended that students use more modern methods in this regard. Teachers began to explain to their students that listening comprehension naturally takes the leading place in language learning, and they began to pay great attention to improving listening skills along with speaking fluency.

By now, the demand and interest in learning foreign languages, especially English has increased so much that from kindergarten age children to senior professionals are trying to learn English. This is a positive situation of course, because learning a language opens doors for personal interests, along with learning the culture, history, and customs of the countries that speak that language.

Many professionals who have been teaching English for a long time are faced with various questions. For instance, what should be used to learn the language easily, what method can be used to improve listening skills, and others? They must consider many aspects to answer such questions because students usually rely on the instructions of teachers they trust and know to be experienced in this regard.

Teachers should be able to use different modern methods in the classroom to teach language and help language learners. The improvement of listening plays an important role in the acquisition of foreign languages. There are several interesting methods to develop listening skills, and these will keep learners interested. Another key skill in language learning is reading and this is more important than listening skills in foreign language classes. In some cases, we can say that one can learn the language better through reading skills.

We usually can show pictures, maps, or diagrams to help students identify the topic of the listening text. Before listening, students can write listening rules and exercises, and then you have to hear them answer the questions. Teach me method: Give some words and phrases to every student, they have to explain the words and phrases to each other in pairs and tell them that they can use the dictionary if necessary. Students can listen or mark what they hear. Chinese hype: Divide the students into two groups and whisper the word to the student at the head of the group and the students must say the word to each other in this way, the last student has to say the word out loud or represent it on the board. Teaching listeners a short song or jazz-related topic. Such methods are effective for developing listening skills and help to improve the ability to remember.

The improvement of the ability to speak is directly related to the skill to hear. In the process of observing young children, we can see that their speech develops through hearing. They listen to how their parents communicate before they say the first word and gradually get used to speech. In addition, they enrich their speech by watching various cartoons. Learning foreign languages is complicated for older people, but it is very easy and effective for young children. They have a better ability to remember what they see or listen to than adults and for this reason, it can be said that children have a high desire to learn languages.

One of the recommended ways to improve listening skills is to use audio and video guides. For example, it is recommended to listen to dialogues, thematic texts, and audio stories and listen to them again from time to time. When we watch audio and video materials, we should pay attention to whether they have subtitles or not in a foreign language because subtitles help to improve speech, listening, and reading skills and also increase vocabulary.

In conclusion, reliance on modern methods and constant repetition of new knowledge has an effective effect on the development of every skill in learning foreign languages.

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